

**LEGO's production challenge:
maintaining process
capability and product
quality while increasing
production volume and
bringing new products to the
market.**

Agenda

- Key Figures
- History
- What is triggering variation?
- Outsourcing – What did we learn?
- Focus areas – to deliver the desired quality
- Guiding principle

At a Glance

Danish family owned

25,382 million
DKK
turnover 2013

Sold in more than
130
countries

Figures per ultimo March 2014.

Production & Distribution Facilities

Consumer Services

TOP 3 complaints:

- Missing parts
- Lost or delayed orders from Shop at Home
- Lost & Replacement parts

phone calls, emails, faxes
and letters per year

Extremely
high
consumer
satisfaction

languages

3 CONTACT
CENTRES

+ some small local teams

Figures per ultimo March 2014.

Turnover

Examples of triggers of variation on moulded elements in connection with growth

Triggers of variation:

- New products (elements)
- New machines
- New technologies
- Process optimization projects
- New colleagues
- Changes in the organization
- New production sites
- Commercial press from sales

Increased risk of losing the overview

Examples of potential problems:

- Changes in the dimensions
- Safety issues (small parts)
- Visual problems (colour, burn marks)
- Processing problems (deform parts)

Potential consequences:

- Decrease of the quality level
- Low customer satisfaction
- Product recall

Moving a mould and getting the desired quality is hard

Growth can be compared with outsourcing
because the culture can't adapt so fast

Moving a mould and getting the desired quality is hard

Learning:

- Moulding is a core competence
- The impact from the LEGO culture on the quality
- Need of more specific quality standards, dimensions and look & feel

Initiatives:

- Definition of key competences
- Improvement of specifications for approval and quality control (alignment, involvement)
- Improvement of measurement methods (internal, external)
- Improve the quality of function test (development of reference elements)
- Assessment of look and feel

Deliver the desired quality: Focus areas

Simplicity

Learning from the past:

- Many small factories in the factory -> difficult overview of daily operation
- Complex material and supplier platform
- Cost of complexity

Focus area:

- Standardize production set-up
- Not only focus on adding new technologies, but also out phasing of old technologies
- Keeping a lean material platform
- Creativity within existing boundaries

Learning from the past:

- Need for more overview
 - Materials
 - Suppliers
 - Production planning
- Firefighting is a bad foundation for improvements

Focus area:

- Physical overview of the technologies: "Simplicity room"
- Visual factory – follow up on the daily production
- Strong Lean-culture

Risk avoidance

Collaboration and knowledge sharing / transfer

Learning from the past:

- The challenge to transfer tacit knowledge
- Culture is the key

Focus areas:

- High level of involvement in decision making
- Work processes support collaboration
- High degree of shared KPIs -> motivate to help
- No blame culture - Focus on the problem
- Problem solving process is important – not only the solution

Guiding principle

"Only the best is good enough"

